

IMPACT OF MONETARY FACTORS ON NIGERIA'S ECONOMIC GROWTH

By

¹⁾ **Onuorah Anastasia Chi-Chi**

Department of Accounting, Banking and Finance,
Delta State University, Asaba Nigeria.

&

²⁾ **Ebiringa, Oforegbunam. Thaddeus**

Department of Management Technology
Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Studying the impact of monetary factors on Nigeria's economic growth has become imperative in the face of the challenges of excess liquidity, poor access to credit, high cost of capital, inflation, and decreasing rate of economic growth. Hence this paper applied econometric modeling in the development of a prediction model for economic growth using critical indices of monetary policy. The results show that there is a significant relationship between money supply, foreign exchange rate and economic growth in Nigeria. However, the possibility of convergence of short-run dynamics of monetary policy factors to long-run equilibrium in economic growth was established. Though, the speed of adjustment with respect to foreign exchange rate was observed to be slow.

Keywords: Cumulative density function, PP Test, Granger causality, Monetary Factors, Exchange rate, money supply.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Monetary policy is the use of the instrument at the disposal of the monetary authority to influence the availability and cost of credit with the ultimate objective of achieving price stability stable economic growth (Folawewo and Osinubi, 2006). Monetary policy is the process by which the government, central bank, or monetary authority of a country controls (i) the supply of money, (ii) availability of money, and (iii) cost of money or rate of interest, in order to attain a set of objectives oriented towards the growth and stability of the economy. Monetary policy according to Shamshad, (2006) rests on the relationship between the rates of interest in an economy, that is the price at which money can be borrowed, and the total supply of money. Monetary policy uses a variety of tools to control one or both of these, to influence outcomes like economic growth, inflation, exchange rates and unemployment.

The failure of monetary authorities in most developing countries, Nigeria in particular to curb price instability has caused unsustainable economic growth (Sanusi, 2002). As many economic indicators show, Nigeria's economy has experienced different growth stages. The GDP growth rate recorded negative growth in the early 1980s (-2.7 in 1982, 7.1 in 1983 and -1.1 in 1984). The growth rate increased steadily between 1985 and 1990 but fell sharply in 1986 and 1987 to 2.5% and -0.2%. Except in 1991 when a negative growth rate of -0.8% was recorded, 1990s witnessed an unstable growth. However, the growth rate has been relatively high since 2001. An examination of the long-term pattern reveals the following secular swings: 1965-1968 Rapid Decline (civil war years), 1969-1971 Revival, 1972-1980 Boom, 1981-1984 Crash, 1985-1991 Renewed Growth, 1992-2010 Wobbling (CBN, 2010). This study aim used selected monetary policy variables to forecast Nigeria's economic growth. The objective is to provide answers to the following research questions:

- To what extent has monetary factors affected economic growth in Nigeria?
- What are the most critical monetary factors for predicting Nigeria's economic growth?.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the past two decades, the shift in the approach of economic management from direct government control to market-based policies has gained momentum, both in the industrial and developing countries. The driving force has been the desire for enhanced efficiency in the mobilisation and utilisation of resources. In this context, an increasing number of countries have embarked on comprehensive adjustment programmes designed to promote a stable macroeconomic environment and provide versatile institutional arrangements necessary for a free market economy. An important element of this adjustment process is the financial sector reform, which helps to establish a solid foundation for effective implementation of the market-based monetary policy.

There are various transmission channels and mechanisms through which monetary policy has affected economic activities by different schools of thought. The transmissions mechanisms of monetary policy have been broadly examined under the monetarist and Keynesian schools of thought. The monetarist transmission mechanism postulates that changes in the money supply lead directly and without going through the financial market, to a change in the real magnitude of money. Thorbecke & Zhang (2008) described this transmission as an increase in open market operations by the Central Bank increases stock of money, which also leads to an increase in Commercial Bank reserves and ability to create credit and hence increase money supply through

the multiplier effect. In order to reduce the quantity of money in their portfolios, the bank and non-bank seller would in the initial stance purchase securities with characteristics equivalent to the ones sold to the Central Bank. The increase in demand bid up to price of such as securities. Thus through this mechanism, the initial increase in money supply, involving the open market operations stimulates activities in the real sector. On the other hand, the Keynesian view of monetary transmission is centred on the ability of changes in money supply to influence the cost of capital through changes in short term interest rates. In this transmission, changes in the money supply work through the financial market to affect the level of economic activities. (Adefeso and Mobolaji, 2010) employed Jahansen maximum likelihood co-integration procedure to show that there is a long run relationship between economic growth, degree of openness, government expenditure and M2. (Ajisafe and Folunso, 2002) observe that that monetary policy exerts significant impact on economic activity in Nigeria.

Monetary policy is a deliberate effort by the monetary authorities (Central Bank) to control the money supply and the credit conditions for the purpose of achieving certain broad economic objectives. Ackley (1978), one of the objectives of the monetary policy, which is the attainment of a high rate of or full employment, does not mean zero unemployment since there is always a certain amount of frictional, voluntary or seasonal unemployment. Gertler and Gilchrist (1991) gave two types of conflicts in the attainment of policy objectives, which are: (i) Necessary Conflict; (ii) Policy Conflict. The necessary conflict exists when the attainment of one objective precludes the attainment of the other that is when the objectives are inherently incompatible. For example, full employment may also conflict with rapid economic growth, which is dependent on the acceptance of innovation and changes, if maintenance of full employment encourages reliance on the status quo. While the policy conflict arises when monetary policy has difficulty in pursuing both goals simultaneously. For example, an easy monetary policy designed to stimulate economic growth will lower the rate of interest and may generate higher inflation if the growth is not sufficient enough to inhibit it. In the works of Thorbecke & Zhang (2008) under the monetary policy indicatives, the indicator of monetary policy provides a scale that permits policy makers to compare the thrust of monetary policy on economic activity that is to characterize one policy as more expensive than another or to characterise policies.

Anyanwu (1996) opined that monetary policy in general refers to the combination of measures designed to regulate the value supply and cost of money in an economy, in consonance with the expected level of economic activity. Ahmed (1991), monetary policy is a central bank's actions to

influence the availability and cost of money and credit, as a means of helping to promote national economic goals. Kogar (1995) observes that monetary policy is an effective instrument in relation to influencing demand. He noted that it is crucial to generating an environment for sustainability of lower inflation. He examined the relationship between financial innovations and monetary control and concluded that in a changing financial structure Central Banks cannot realize efficient monetary policy without setting new procedures and instruments in the long-run, because profit seeking financial institutions change or create new instruments in order to evade regulations or respond to the economic conditions in the economy.

Monetary policy in the economy is made up of six components or different policies dealing with the volume of or quantity of, money i.e. the supply of money and credit, its price, the rate of interest and its allocation (Afolabi, 1991). It also includes policies on balance of payments on the exchange rates and on external reserve management. In other words, monetary policy that limits itself merely to establishing and controlling the quantity of money or its price or indeed omits or excludes any of the six components is not complete and cannot be effective.

Folawewo and Osinubi, (2006) investigated how monetary policy objective of controlling inflation rate and intervention in the financing of fiscal deficits affect the variability of inflation and real exchange rate. The analysis is done using a rational expectation framework that incorporates the fiscal role of exchange rate. It was shown in the paper that the effort of monetary policy at influencing the finance of government fiscal deficit through the determination of the inflation-tax rate affects both the rate of inflation and the real exchange rate, thereby causing volatility in their rates. The paper revealed that inflation affects volatility of its own rate as well as the rate of real exchange. The policy implication of the paper is that monetary policy should be set in such a way that the objective it is to achieve is well defined.

Sanusi (2002) opined that the ability of the CBN to pursue an effective monetary policy in a globalised and rapidly integrated financial market environment depends on several factors. These include: instituting appropriate legal framework, institutional structure and conducive political environment, which allows the Bank to operate with reference to exercising its instrument and operational autonomy in decision- making; the degree of coordination between monetary and fiscal policies to ensure consistency and complementarities; the overall macroeconomic environment, including the stage of development, depth and stability of the financial markets as well as the efficiency of the payments and settlement systems; the level and adequacy of information and communication facilities; and the availability of consistent, adequate, reliable, high quality and

timely information to the Bank. He stressed that seeking a proper role for monetary policy in promoting strong and sustainable growth in a stable macroeconomic environment in Nigeria is an on-going challenge for the Central Bank.

Monetary policy presupposes a form of relationship between supply of and demand for money on one hand, and other aggregate economic variables like general price level, output, income, savings and investment on the other hand (Anyanwu, 1996). This assumed relationship influences the mix of policy instrument used and its effectiveness. There are the monetarist viewpoints represented by Milton Friedman, the Keynesian school and lastly the one represented by Raddiffe (Anyanwu, 1996).

Friedman(1963) is of the view that changes in the stock of money are closely related to changes in the price level and through it, on other general economic aggregates. But, precision and rigidity in this relationship is distorted because of changes in output and the amount of money that the public desires to hold relative to its income (Mohsin (2005)). The effects of these changes are not to be seen as instantaneous as there is sometimes lag between the application of the monetary policy and its effectiveness (Sanusi, 2002).

Keynesian viewpoint is that money plays a role in the determination of real output, general price level and other Macro-economic variables. According to them, national income depends on the interplay between such variables as expected rate of profit and interest. The rate of interest is a function of the supply of and the demand for money. Equilibrium income depends on two conditions in this model, that is:

- Planned saving must be equal to planned investment, and,
- At any point in time, supply of money must equal demand for money.

But both savings, investment, demand for and supply of money is influenced by changes in the rate of interest (Anyanwu, 1996).

Within this content, monetary policy will consist of altering the rate of interest to achieve the desired trend in the economy. The effectiveness of monetary policy will then depend on the interest elasticity of demand for money. Here, monetary policy is likely to be effective, the more the less interest elastic the demand for idle balances, and the less interest elastic the demand for idle balances, and the less interest elastic the investment and consumption schedule that depend on active or transaction balances. Therefore, the effectiveness will be in combating depression rather than inflation (Anyanwu, 1996).

The third viewpoint represented by Raddiffe is a variant of the Keynesian school of thought. A distinction is made between the demand for money and the demand for liquidity. These two types of demand are not the same thing because there exist interest yielding money substitutes, which people can easily turn to cash whenever they want. As a result of this situation, whatever is done to change the demand for money may be less effective than expected, because it is the demand that will respond to interest rate changes? The amount of money desired may not increase, if the interest rate falls even though the amount of liquidity increases. Part of the accumulation of liquidity is likely to take the form of interest bearing near-money instead of non-interest yielding cash. The results obtained from changing the money supply depend on shifts in the demand for money and not on short-run interest elasticity of demand for money.

There monetary policy confirmed to regulating money supply is not likely to be successful in stemming inflation, since the significant variable is not money per se, but the supply relative to the demand for it. And the flexibility of demand for money makes the control of money supply alone, an unreliable tool of monetary policy. Therefore, for monetary policy to be effective it has to address itself to the control of the volume, cost and direction of liquidity rather than money supply in the economy (Batini, N. (2004)).

The Central Bank has at its disposal a number of control mechanisms usually referred to as "tools of monetary policy". Some of these tools are quantitative while others are selective (Sanusi, 2002).

3.1 Methodology

The sources of data are the publications of Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) such as CBN statistical bulletin, CBN statements of Accounts and annual reports, as well as the National Bureau of Statistics. The relevant variables sourced include: Lending Rate (LR), Money Supply (MS), Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Foreign Exchange Rate (FER) and Domestic Credit (DC) between the periods 1981 to 2010. The method of data analysis adopts include Ordinary Least Square Estimate (OLES), Diagnostic Test procedure, Unit Root test Using Phillips perron Test (PP), Granger Causality Test and Vector Auto Regressive Model (VAR). also the Cumulative Density Functions (CDF) is used to test the structural stability of the model developed.

3.2 Model Specification

To empirically evaluate the effectiveness of monetary policy instruments (MS, LR, DC and FER) on the economic growth (GDP) in Nigeria, there is need to specify the model parameters, the model and the apriori.

LNGDP= log of Gross Domestic Product

LNMS= log of Money Supply

LNFER= Log of Foreign Exchange Rate

The model

LNGDP=f(Monetary factors)

The data transformation model of absolute change is presented mathematically as:

$$RLNGDP = f(RLNMS, RLNLR, RLNDC, RLNFER)$$

$$\Delta RLNGDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \Delta RLNMS + \alpha_2 \Delta RLNFER + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta RLNGDP_{t+1} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \Delta RLNMS_{t-1} + \alpha_2 \Delta RLNFER_{t-1} + VAR(\delta) \quad (2)$$

To substantiate the empirical approach to the monetary policy instruments for economic growth in Nigeria, the apriori expectations are defined by the regression coefficients $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 > 0$, these are referred to sign directions and size of the parameters in economic relationships.

4.1 Results and Discussions

The results of the empirical study are discussed as follows:

Table 1: Summary of Result of Unit Root Test using Phillips Perron (PP)

Variables	PP Test	5% Critical Value	Decision	Conclusion
D(LNGDP) I(1)	-3.1712	-2.9850	No Unit Root	Stationary
D(LNMS) I(1)	-4.1990	-2.9665	No Unit Root	Stationary
D(LNFER)I(1)	-15.914	-2.9705	No Unit Root	Stationary

**significant at 5% level, PP test > Critical value, then the variable is stationary*

Source: E-Views 7.0

Table 1 shows that there is no unit root among the variables subjected to Phillips Perron (PP) test at various level and order difference. The variables: GDP, Money Supply (LNMS) and Foreign Exchange Rate (LNFER) are stationary at order 1 as the PP-test statistic is greater than the critical value at 5%.

Table 2 Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:			
LNMS does not Granger Cause LNGDP	28	3.10197	0.06416
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNMS		2.24152	0.12901
LNFER does not Granger Cause LNGDP	28	0.98968	0.38698
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFER		1.01997	0.37635
LNFER does not Granger Cause LNMS	28	2.99973	0.06956
LNMS does not Granger Cause LNFER		0.20674	0.81473

Source: E-Views 7.0

The causality points out effect of monetary policy instruments on GDP are significant in explaining the causal effect on the economic growth. In other words, Foreign Exchange Rate (LNFER) Granger causes economic growth (LNGDP) and LNGDP does not granger cause LNFER. More so, Monetary Supply (LNMS) granger causes economic growth (LNGDP) and LNGDP (economic growth) does not granger cause LNMS. These imply a short run causality effect of money supply and foreign exchange rate on Nigeria's economic growth. Hence, Money Supply (LNMS) and foreign exchange rate (LNFER) are influential monetary policy variables for determining economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 3: Test of Co integration among series

Series: LNGDP LNMS LNFER

Lags interval: No lags

Eigenvalue	Likelihood Ratio	5 Percent Critical Value	1 Percent Critical Value	Hypothesized No. of CE(s)
0.773187	67.60092	29.68	35.65	None **
0.430087	24.57570	15.41	20.04	At most 1 **
0.248111	2.269842	3.76	6.65	At most 2

*(**) denotes rejection of the hypothesis at 5%(1%) significance level L.R. rejects any co integration at 5% significance level.

Unnormalized Cointegrating Coefficients:

LNGDP	LNMS	LNFER
18.94067	2.746802	0.036881
129.0671	93.01259	-0.009821
-218.0898	48.90542	0.001365

Normalized
Cointegrating
Coefficients: 1
Cointegrating
Equation(s)

LNGDP	LNMS	LNFER	C
1.000000	0.145021 (0.58181)	0.001947 (0.00265)	0.000737
Log likelihood	223.9943		

Normalized
Cointegrating
Coefficients: 2
Cointegrating
Equation(s)

LNGDP	LNMS	LNFER	C
1.000000	0.000000	0.002457 (0.00472)	0.000170
0.000000	1.000000	-0.003515 (0.00685)	0.003910
Log likelihood	232.1472		

Source: E-Views

From Table 3, the trace statistic and likelihood function p-values, revealed that there is cointegration at most 1 with at least 2 cointegrating equation among the variables were rejected in favour of the alternative hypotheses at 5 per cent. This is because their values exceed the critical values at the 0.05 level which implies that a long-run relationship exists among the variables (LNGDP, LNMS and LNFER). It can equally be seen from Table 6 that there are at least two cointegrating equations in the series. Thus, we report the non normalized cointegrating equation, which was at LNMS. The results from the cointegrating equations in Table 6 above suggest that all the variables in the two equations are significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 4: Vector Autoregressive Model

Standard errors & t-statistics in parentheses

	LNGDP	LNMS	LNFER
LNGDP(-1)	8.47E-17 (2.1E-16) (0.40402)	-3.39E-16 (4.7E-16) (-0.72604)	-3.47E-13 (6.8E-13) (-0.51233)
LNGDP(-2)	-1.46E-16 (1.7E-16) (-0.85397)	2.33E-16 (3.8E-16) (0.61384)	-2.39E-13 (5.5E-13) (-0.43315)
LNMS(-1)	-2.21E-16 (7.0E-17) (-3.15050)	0.000000 (1.6E-16) (0.00000)	1.33E-13 (2.3E-13) (0.58750)
LNMS(-2)	-2.01E-17 (7.3E-17) (-0.27687)	1.61E-16 (1.6E-16) (0.99508)	7.22E-14 (2.4E-13) (0.30720)
LNFER(-1)	1.34E-20 (2.8E-20) (0.48409)	-2.68E-20 (6.2E-20) (-0.43496)	-1.47E-16 (9.0E-17) (-1.63693)
LNFER(-2)	-2.91E-20 (2.8E-20) (-1.03106)	-5.81E-20 (6.3E-20) (-0.92641)	-3.97E-17 (9.1E-17) (-0.43581)
C	-1.22E-18 (3.3E-19) (-3.64901)	-1.25E-18 (7.4E-19) (-1.68137)	1.35E-15 (1.1E-15) (1.24578)
LNGDP	1.000000 (2.2E-16) (4.5E+15)	-1.68E-16 (4.9E-16) (-0.34156)	6.87E-13 (7.1E-13) (0.96409)
LNMS	-2.26E-18 (6.7E-17) (-0.03394)	1.000000 (1.5E-16) (6.8E+15)	8.62E-14 (2.1E-13) (0.40089)
LNFER	1.63E-20 (2.5E-20) (0.65541)	0.000000 (5.5E-20) (0.00000)	1.000000 (8.1E-17) (1.2E+16)
R-squared	0.99780	1.000000	1.000000
Adj. R-squared	0.89765	1.000000	1.000000
Sum sq. resids	4.75E-36	2.35E-35	4.96E-29
S.E. equation	5.14E-19	1.14E-18	1.66E-15
F-statistic	5.89E+30	7.64E+30	2.88E+31
Mean dependent	-0.000675	-0.003332	0.223989

S.D. dependent	0.000720	0.001824	5.138721
Determinant Residual Covariance		2.20E-103	
Log Likelihood		3190.126	
Akaike Information Criteria		-225.7233	
Schwarz Criteria		-224.2959	

Source: E-Views7.0

The VAR model of the study shows that the possibility of convergence from the short-run dynamics to the long-run equilibrium between the selected variables; however, the speeds of adjustment among the variables were observed to be slow. In addition, the causality in VAR and Wald tests point out that past value of LNMS is significant in explaining the values of LNGDP in the current year (-1). On the other hand, the value of the joint significance indicates that the current values of LNMS are most influential in determining the current values of LNGDP (-1). This underscores that what influence economic growth in Nigeria is the level of money injected into the Nigerian economy. The individual magnitudes effects of the independent variable on the dependent variable can be explained by 89.7% while about 10.7% cannot be explained as a result of factors such as policy and political terrain of the nation. In addition, there is 99% degree of association between the monetary policy instruments and economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 5: ACF/PACF Results

Included observations: 30

Correlations are asymptotically consistent approximations

LNGDP, LNMS(-i)	LNGDP, LNMS(+i)	i	lag	lead
. * .	. * .	0	-0.0543	-0.0543
. * .	. ** .	1	-0.0926	-0.2226
. ***.	. * .	2	0.2633	0.1246
. .	. ** .	3	-0.0396	0.2101
.*** .	. * .	4	-0.2562	0.0521
. ** .	. .	5	-0.1478	0.0122
. ** .	. ** .	6	-0.1534	-0.1528
. ** .	.*** .	7	-0.1477	-0.3240
. .	.*** .	8	0.0347	-0.3134
. * .	.*** .	9	0.1408	-0.3245
. ****.	. ** .	10	0.3796	-0.1800
. ** .	. * .	11	0.2181	-0.1007
. ***.	. .	12	0.3314	-0.0378
. * .	. .	13	0.1074	0.0147
. ***.	. .	14	0.2567	0.0403

. * .	. * .	15	0.1215	0.0737
. .	. .	16	0.0077	0.0126

Included observations: 30

Correlations are asymptotically consistent approximations

LNGDP, LNFER(-i)	LNGDP, LNFER(+i)	i	lag	lead
. * .	. * .	0	0.0814	0.0814
. * .	.*** .	1	0.1303	-0.3154
.** .	. .	2	-0.1825	-0.0228
. .	. ** .	3	-0.0328	0.2392
.** .	. * .	4	-0.2212	0.1545
. ***.	. * .	5	0.2993	0.1119
. .	. .	6	-0.0085	-0.0206
. * .	. .	7	0.0994	-0.0083
. * .	. .	8	0.0600	-0.0112
. .	. .	9	0.0017	-0.0101
. * .	. .	10	-0.0443	-0.0111
. .	. .	11	0.0361	-0.0094
. .	. .	12	0.0164	-0.0098
. * .	. .	13	0.1029	-0.0080
. * .	. .	14	-0.0852	-0.0055
. * .	. .	15	-0.0571	-0.0091
.*** .	. .	16	-0.3994	-0.0108

Forecasting model of ARMA show that

LNGDP	LNMS	LNFER	C
1.000000	0.145021	0.001947	0.000737
	(0.58181)	(0.00265)	

$$LNGD = 0.000737 + 0.1450LNMS + 0.0019LNFER \dots 4.1$$

The forecasted model at lag 16 reveals that LNMS and LNFER are statistically significant with about 14.5% and 0.1% magnitude strength of predicting LNGDP. This indicates that only money supply exert the greater evidence of predicting economic growth in Nigeria. The structural trend analysis of the LNGDP with respect to the monetary factors showed that there is an upward movement of GDP to the money supply but downward movement with foreign exchange rate.

Fig 1a,b and c

5.0 Findings

The existence of a variety of debatable discourse regarding the level of effectiveness of Nigeria's monetary policy on economic growth motivated this research study. The literature has also contributed to the foregoing on the effective measures of monetary policy instruments on economic growth in Nigeria. The theories focus on the effect, impact forecasting and relationship between the monetary factors on economic growth in Nigeria. The study employed econometric tools to analyze time series data sourced from CBN Statistical Bulletin (1980-2010) and analyzed econometric tools. The identified structure and trends of the money policy instruments that are responsible for economic growth in Nigeria were studied through Cumulative Distribution functions of variables.

6.0 Conclusion

The results from the econometric analyses show that there is a short-run relationship between the effective control of money supply and rate of growth of Nigeria's economy. The results obtained from the cointegration analysis indicates at least one co-integrating equation exist among the monetary

policy instruments and economic growth. The study confirms that in Nigeria, the most critical factors that influence the level of economic growth are level of money supply and exchange rate of the domestic currency. Meanwhile, the identified active factor; LNMS have directly influence economic growth both in the previous year and current indicating long run effective monetary policy instrument of measuring economic growth. The VAR model of the study showed the possibility of convergence from the short-run dynamics to the long-run equilibrium between the selected variables; monetary policy instruments and economic growth; however, the speeds of adjustment among the variables were observed to be slow in terms of foreign exchange rate. In addition, the causality result point out that the current study reveal that LNMS and LNFER granger cause economic growth (LNGDP) in Nigeria.

7.0 Policy Implication

The study has critically demonstrated that the major monetary policy instruments responsible for the economic growth in Nigeria and the effective performance are money supply and low lending rate. It therefore suffice to make substantial policies with high implementation of such policies collectively made be adopted by policy analyst, economist, key players in the National economic planning to reduce the lending rate as monetary instruments for economic growth.

8.0 Recommendation

From the empirical results, the study proffers the following recommendations:

Firstly, Massive and expansionary investment policy should be put in place capable of creating rapid growth of money supply to the real sector of the economy that would promote productivity and openness in the economy that can reduce inflation, discouragement high interest rate to enable investors have access to credit facility with low interest which will in turn increase both investment thereby increasing economic growth in Nigeria.

Secondly, money supply as monetary factor can effectively forecast impact on economic development therefore, effort should be made by the government to manage the supply of money function in the right direction to achieve maximum economic growth in Nigeria.

Thirdly, Nigeria government should develop economic structure that can compete favourable with the international community's which will be characterized by high investment inflows into the

country therefore improving the real foreign exchange rate in Nigeria for better economic development and growth.

References

- [1] Ackley, G. (1978) *Macroeconomics: Theory and Policy*. New York: Macmillan.
- [2] A. Ahmed (1991) "Indirect Monetary Control in Nigeria, Problems and Prospects". *CBN Research Department Occasional Papers*, No. 1 December 2.
- [3] A. O. Folawewo and T. S. Osinubi (2006) "Monetary Policy and Macroeconomic Instability in Nigeria: A Rational Expectation Approach". *Journal of Social Science*, Vol. 12, No. 2, pp.93-100.
- [4] Central Bank of Nigeria (2010) Annual Report and Statement of Accounts. Abuja: Central Bank of Nigeria.
- [6] Central Bank of Nigeria (2009) Statistical Bulletin. Abuja: Central Bank of Nigeria.
- [7] C. I. Kogar (1995) "Financial Innovations and Monetary Control". *The Central Bank of The Republic of Turkey Discussion Paper*, No. 9515, May.
- [8] Mohsin (2005). Inflation in Pakistan: Money or Wheat, Paper presented in SBP conference.
- [9] J.C. Anyanwu (1996) *Monetary Economics: Theory, Policy and Institutions*. Hybrid Publishers Limited, Nigeria.
- [10] K. F. Duncan, and M. Sidrauski (1971) *Monetary and Fiscal Policy in a Growing Economy*.
- [11] L. Afolabi (1991) *Monetary Economics*. Heinemann Educational Books (Nigeria) Plc.
- [12] M. Friedman and A. Schwartz (1963) "Money and Business Cycles", *Review of Economics and Statistics*, February, pp. 32-64.
- [13] M. Gertler and S. Gilchrist (1991) "Monetary Policy, Business Cycles and the Behaviour of Small Manufacturing Firms". *National Bureau of Economic Research, Cambridge*, No. WP 3892.
- [15] S. D. Oliner and G. D. Rudebusch (1995) "Is There a Bank Lending Channel for Monetary Policy?" *Economic Review, Federal Reserve Bank of San Francisco*, No. 2, pp.3-20.
- [16] Sanusi, J. O. (2002) "Central Bank and the macroeconomic environment in Nigeria". No. 24 of the national Institute for Policy and Strategic Studies (NIPSS), Kuru on 19th August.
- [17] Adefeso, H. and Mobolaji, H. (2010) 'The fiscal- monetary policy and economic growth in Nigeria: further empirical evidence', *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, Vol. 7(2) Pp 142
- [18] Batini, N. (2004) 'Achieving and maintaining price stability in Nigeria'. IMF Working Paper WP/04/97, June.
- [19] Thorbecke & Zhang (2008). *Monetary Policy Surprises & Interest Rates: Choosing between the Inflation-Revelation & Excess Sensitivity Hypotheses*, RIETI Discussion Paper Series.

[20] Shamshad (2006). Perspectives on Pakistan's Monetary Policy Developments, Address as Chief Guest at the Woodrow Wilson Centre, Washington D.C